

THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S SPEECH IN THE PROCESS OF COMMUNICATION AND PLAY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7583929>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th January 2023

Accepted: 29th January 2023

Online: 30th January 2023

KEY WORDS

Foreign language, teachers, basic communication skills, speech development, etc.

ABSTRACT

Speech and language communication enables children to build positive relationships, form friendships and learn by listening, talking and questioning. Good speech, language and communication skills have a positive impact on confidence and self-esteem. This article delves into the details about The development of children's speech in the process of communication and play.

By interacting and playing using speech and language, a child or young person develops social skills and friendships that support their well-being. As children learn and use new vocabulary, they gain confidence in speech and learn to express their feelings which will mean that their needs are met. Good speech, language and communication skills support educational achievement and employment opportunities. If a child or young person has difficulties with speech, language and communication, they are more likely to have difficulty in developing reading and writing skills, have behaviour difficulties and difficulty in forming friendships and making social connections. Difficulty in expressing themselves causes frustration and isolation. Many children and young people with speech, language and communication difficulties have significant behavioural difficulties or are withdrawn which may result in a negative impact on confidence and self-esteem. Poor communication has an impact on mental health, employment opportunities and links closely to poor educational achievement and poverty.

The correctional orientation of the pedagogical process is especially pronounced and strengthened in the content and working methods of a speech therapist, psychologist, social teacher, educators who implement the recommendations of specialists. Adaptive function is manifested:

- in activities related to adaptation to the conditions of preschool education, upon admission to kindergarten;
- in a gradual increase in the intensity of the load (training effect of classes); the complexity of educational material from the beginning to the middle of the year;
- to increase the adaptive and adaptive capabilities of children under the influence of the regimen of the day, taking adaptogens, hardening, exercising in the air, etc.

The prognostic function is based on repeated diagnostics aimed at predicting the intermediate and final results of activity, taking into account the capabilities of children, teachers, and conditions of pre-school education. The most relevant and difficult for educators

is the development of technologies for the education and training of preschool children. Technological structuring and modeling of classes, their orientation to the leading type of activity - the game, creates the organizational framework of work, and determines the effectiveness of the methods and techniques used. The formation of a steady interest in the acquisition of knowledge by children, the manifestation of individuality and creativity is facilitated by classes with modernized structures. It is aimed at helping each person to express themselves in life and find harmony of the soul, already starting with the first step taken in a preschool. And this, in turn, involves the development of modern trends in the theory and practice of preschool education - a reflection in the content of increasing socialization and pedagogization of the entire system of preschool education, which allows us to determine the separation of the institution from the parental environment and the sociocultural sphere in which the child lives.

In general, the importance of preschool education is underestimated. Too often it is overlooked that this is an extremely important step in a person's life, on which the fundamental principle of a person's personal qualities is laid. And the point is not in quantitative indicators of the "coverage" of children or the satisfaction of the desires of parents. Kindergartens, nurseries, combines are not just a means of "looking after" the children, their mental, moral and physical development takes place here, as well as work is underway on the social adaptation of the child. With the transition to teaching children from 6 years old, kindergartens faced new problems for themselves - organizing the activities of preparatory groups so that children could adapt normally to the school rhythm of life and have self-care skills. Of particular importance is the analysis of the society's orientation towards supporting preschool forms of education, and the willingness of parents to resort to their help to prepare their children for work and rational organization of their social and personal life. In order to understand the specifics of this form of education, the position and value orientations of those people who work with children — educators, maintenance personnel — and their readiness, understanding, and desire to fulfill their responsibilities and hopes are especially significant.

The first signs of communication occur when an infant learns that a cry will bring food, comfort, and companionship. Newborns also begin to recognize important sounds in their environment, such as the voice of their mother or primary caretaker. As they grow, babies begin to sort out the speech sounds that compose the words of their language. By 6 months of age, most babies recognize the basic sounds of their native language. Children vary in their development of speech and language skills. However, they follow a natural progression or timetable for mastering the skills of language. Language development is always in line with the growth of the child. Parents should always pay attention to these development, because at this time, largely determines the learning process. This can be done by giving a good example, to motivate children to learn. Parents are largely responsible for the success of children's learning and should always strive to improve the potential of children in order to develop optimally. In view of its function, language is the ability to communicate with others. There are significant differences between the understanding of language and speech. Languages include all forms of communication, both expressed in the form of oral, written, sign language, gestures, facial expressions, pantomim or art. However, spoken language is the most effective

form of communication, and the most important and widely used. Language is the ability to communicate with others. There are significant differences between the understanding of language and speech. Language includes all forms of communication, whether expressed orally, written, used signs, gestures, or facial expressions. While the speech is a spoken language that is the most effective form of communication and considered most important and widely used. Language development increases through the growth of the children. Parents should always pay attention to these developments, since it will determine the learning process. This can be done by giving a good example to motivate children to learn and so forth. Parents are greatly responsible for the success of children' learning and should always strive to improve children's potential in order to develop optimally.

Behaviourists found children born without bringing any ability. Thus the child must learn through conditioning of the environment, the process of imitation, and given reinforcement. An expert looked at the development of language from the point of stimulus-response, which saw thinking as an internal process of language begin to accrue from interactions in the environment. The other one looked at the development of language from the point of social learning theory. Other argued that children learn by doing, imitations or simulate a model that meant not having received a reinforcement from others. English teaching is done in stages. Similarly, learning Indonesian children do not directly speak, read and write simultaneously. Before they could speak Bahasa they should listen first. Speaking Once the child is often heard in English, children can be encouraged to speak in simple sentences. For example, by applying time of 30 minutes a day for a family to speak in English. Like the newly age children start talking, children also start talking in English although with one word like 'book' when they saw their brother brings a book.

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